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Research Article

Study of the Seasonal Variation in the Physico-Chemical Parameters of a Tropical Reservoir

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ABSTRACT

The physico-chemical parameters of Ado-Ekiti Reservoir in Southwest region of Nigeria were investigated from May 2002 to July 2004. Monthly mean values of the parameters were; Temperature $27.7^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.60$ (range 23.50°C to 30.04°C); Transparency $0.99\text{m} \pm 0.26$ (range 0.51 to 1.54m); pH 8.39 (range 5.63 to 9.82mg/l); Dissolved Oxygen (DO) $5.7 \pm 1.47\text{mg/l}$ (Range 4.08 to 8.98mg/l, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) $1.90 \pm 0.61\text{mg/l}$ (range 0.93 to 3.20 mg/l); Alkalinity $45 \pm 19.40\text{mg CaCO}_3/\text{l}$ (range 22.0 to 100.88 CaCO_3/l); Free Carbon dioxide $24.61 \pm 8.50\text{ppm}$ (range 16.50 to 47.50ppm). Results showed monthly variations of the physico-chemical parameters in the reservoir. Correlation coefficients (r) for all pairs of determined physico-chemical parameters showed that transparency had a significant correlation with Dissolved Oxygen (0.52) and pH (0.63) ($p \leq 0.05$ and 0.01 levels). Alkalinity had a positive correlation with pH (0.43) and low negative correlation (-0.30; -0.21) with DO and Free Carbon dioxide. Abundance of *Hepsetus odoe* positively correlated with dissolved oxygen and free carbon dioxide ($r = 0.36$ and 0.31) and negatively with pH, BOD and temperature ($r = -0.20, 0.19, -0.01$) respectively. These correlations were insignificant ($p \geq 0.05$ level). All the values fell within recommended range for fish production.

Keywords: physico-chemical parameters, Tropical Reservoir, Abundance of *H. odoe*.

INTRODUCTION

Limnological studies include the physico-chemical and biological parameters of fresh waters. These parameters are used to analyze the quality of water (Goldman and Horne, 1983; Boyd and Tucker, 1998). The physical and chemical characteristics of water bodies affect the species composition, abundance, productivity and physiological conditions of aquatic organisms (Bagenal, 1978). Economic development and population growth require stable water and hydroelectric power supplies. However, because of the relative scarcity of natural lakes, it will be expected that tropical countries will construct reservoirs in parallel with their economic development, thereby making reservoirs the predominant lake type in many regions (Lewis, 2000). This leads to the conclusion that in tropics as a whole, limnology must be strongly oriented towards reservoirs than it has been at temperate latitudes. Lakes and reservoirs around the globe are critical components in the ecological system. They provide habitat, sanctuary and food for many species of fish and wildlife and are also a source of process water to a myriad of industries (Dinar *et al.*, 1995).

Nigeria is richly blessed with a vast area of inland waters. The total surface area of water bodies in Nigeria is estimated to be about 14,991, 900 hectares ($149,919\text{km}^2$) and this constitutes about 15.9% of the total area of Nigeria (Ita, 1993). These include both natural and man-made lakes, reservoirs, floodplains and cattle ponds, rivers and streams; but exclude deltas, estuarine and miscellaneous wetlands suitable for rice cultivation. The species composition and density of aquatic organisms will be influenced not only by geographical locations but also by water quality of their aquatic habitats. This can in turn be adversely affected by human activities (Oben, 2000, Atobatele and Ugwumba, 2008).

Many workers have investigated the physico-chemistry of Nigerian freshwater bodies especially in the southwest. These authors include: Egborge (1970) on River Osun, Adebisi (1981) on Upper River Ogun, Oke (1998) on Owena Reservoir, Oben (2000) on three man-made lakes in Ibadan, Akin-Oriola (2003) on Ogunpa and Oyan Lakes, Idowu and Ugwumba (2005) on Eleyele Reservoir, Ayoade *et al* (2006) on comparative studies of Oyan and Asejire Lakes, Atobatele and Ugwumba (2008) on Aiba Reservoir, Oso and Fagbuaro (2008) on Ero Reservoir.

Limnology plays an important role in decision making process for pollution control and aquaculture enhancement. Researches on the limnological aspects are of paramount significance in developing fresh water quality. Therefore water quality is a paramount factor in ecosystem productivity. The present study is to investigate the physico-chemical parameters of Ado-Ekiti Reservoir and the effects on abundance of African pike

H. odoe, one of the major commercial catch in the reservoir. The physico-chemical parameters of the water will reveal the state of the reservoir in terms of its suitability for fishery activities and for domestic uses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Ado-Ekiti Reservoir was constructed by damming the Ireje River in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria in 1958 for the supply of water for domestic uses and production of fish for the people of Ado-Ekiti and its environs (Agbeyo, 1976). At full capacity, the reservoir contains about 47 millions gallons of water (Ebisemiju, 1993). The author further reported that the reservoir has a catchment area of 32.50km² and total annual discharge of 9.137 millions/m³ of water. The reservoir is situated on an undulating plane of an average height of 440m above sea level and surrounded by highlands. The reservoir lies between latitude 7° 35' - 7° 36' North and longitude 5° 12' - 5° 13' East of the Equator as shown in figure 1

Sampling

Bimonthly sampling was carried out from May, 2002 to July 2004. On each occasion, sampling was between 08.00 and 10.30am. Surface water samples were collected from each sampling station with plastic bottles for chemical analysis. Laboratory investigations were carried out at the Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Water temperature was determined in the field using mercury-in-glass thermometer graduated in degree celcius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). The thermometer was allowed to stabilize for 5 minutes in surface water and was read while still in water. Transparency values were obtained in the field using asecchi disc as described by Ruttner (1963). The pH of the water samples was determined using Kent pH meter, 7020 model. Dissolved Oxygen concentration (DO) and Bichemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Alkalinity were determined using the titrimetric method described by Mackereth (1963). Free Carbon dioxide was determined using the titrimetric methods described by Kumar (1992).

Relative Abundance of *H. odoe*

Information on the relative abundance of *H. odoe* was obtained from the occurrence of the species from weekly samples collected from the landing centre of the local fishermen. The numbers encountered were added to obtain monthly occurrence. The results were expressed as percentage number relative to total fish catch.

Statistical Analysis

The physico-chemical parameters determined and *H. odoe* percentage abundance were subjected to correlation coefficient (r) analysis.

Results

Fig. 2: Monthly variations in physico-chemical parameters of Ado-Ekiti Reservoir, May 2002 — July 2004

The pattern of monthly variations in the physico-chemical parameters for the study period is shown in figure 2. Monthly surface water temperature ranged from 23.50°C – 30.04°C with mean of 27.70°C ± 1.6. Between May and October (wet season), 2002, temperature of surface water ranged from 25.90 to 28.10°C and from November 2003 to April 2004 (dry season) the range was 28.00 to 30.04°C. The highest surface water temperature of 30.04°C was recorded in March 2004, while the lowest value of 23.50°C was in December, 2002. Transparency of the water ranged from 0.51 to 1.54m with mean value of 0.99m ± 0.26. Low water transparency (0.51 – 0.87m) was recorded between May and October 2002, while higher values (1.17 – 1.24m) were between November, 2002 and January, 2003. There was a drop in transparency from March 2004 to July 2004 (1.09 – 0.75m). Throughout the period of sampling, February 2004 had the highest transparency value (1.54m) while the lowest value (0.51m) was in September, 2002.

The pH of the water ranged between 5.63 and 9.82. The higher pH of 9.8 was recorded in October, 2003 followed by January, 2004 (9.78) while the lowest value of 5.63 was in June, 2004. Dissolved Oxygen concentration (DO) of the water varied from 4.08 to 8.98mg/l with mean of 5.70mg/l ± 1.47. The lowest dissolved oxygen concentration was observed in September. Generally dissolved oxygen was highest in December, 2002, 8.90mg/l when temperature (23.50°C) was lowest. Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) ranged from 0.93 to 3.20mg/l with mean of 1.90 ± 0.61mg/l. Highest BOD value was recorded in December 2002 (3.20mg/l) when DO was highest. The least value was in April (0.93mg/l).

Alkalinity ranged from 22.0 to 100.88mg CaCO₃/l with mean value of 45.2mg CaCO₃/l ± 19.4. The highest value of 100.88 mgCaCO₃/l was recorded in September, 2003 followed by 74.0mg CaCO₃/l in November while the lowest value of 22.0mg CaCO₃/l was recorded in May, 2002. Free Carbon dioxide ranged from 50 to 47.50ppm. The highest value of 47.50 was recorded in May 2002 while the lowest value was in October 2003 (16.50ppm).

Table 1: Correlation coefficient (r) values of physic-chemical parameters and abundance of *Hepsetus odoe* of Ado Ekiti Reservoir

Abundance of <i>H. odoe</i> . (Number)	Alkalinity (CaCO ₃ /l)	BOD mg/l	Dissolved oxygen DO (mg/l)	Free carbon dioxide (ppm)	pH	Temperature (°C)	Transparency (m)
Abundance of <i>H. odoe</i>	0.03	-0.19	0.36	0.31	-0.20	-0.01	0.02
Alkalinity		0.03	-0.30	-0.21	0.43	0.28	0.09
BOD			0.21	-0.45	0.10	-0.07	0.22
Dissolved Oxygen 0.52*					-0.45	-0.09	0.03
Free carbon dioxide					-0.64**	-0.19	-0.54
pH 0.63**							0.47
Temperature 0.35							
Transparency							

*Correlation is significant at 0.05% level (2 – tailed)

**Correlation is significant at 0.01% level (2 – tailed)

Table 1 shows the correlation coefficients (r) for all pairs of determined physico-chemical parameters. Transparency had a significant correlation with dissolved oxygen (0.52) and pH (0.63) ($P \leq 0.05$ and 0.01 levels). Alkalinity had a high positive correlation with pH (0.43) and low negative correlation (-0.30, -0.21) with DO and free carbon dioxide.

Abundance of *H. odoe* positively correlated with dissolved oxygen and free carbon-dioxide ($r = 0.36$ and 0.31) and negatively with pH, BOD and temperature ($r = -0.20, 0.19, -0.01$ respectively). (see table 1). These correlations were insignificant ($P \geq 0.05$ level).

DISCUSSION

The marked variation and significant differences in physico-chemical qualities of the water indicate different environmental conditions. These variations may be related to patterns of water use, temperature and rainfall (Ayoade *et al.*, 2006; Atobatele and Ugwumba, 2008; Oso and Fagbenro, 2008). Temperature is an important factor that influences primary production in reservoirs. (Lewis 2000). It depends on the climate, sun light and depth and does not undergo drastic changes during the year in lacustrine environments (Egborge, 1970; Gupta & Gupta, 2006; Akinyemi&Nwakwo, 2006; Atobatele&Ugwumba, 2008) as compared to fluvial environments. Water temperature was generally low during the period of heavy rainfall probably because of the cooling effects of the rains and high relative humidity which could reduce evaporation of water. The lowest water temperature recorded in December 2002 coincided with the period of extreme harmattan for that year. Adebayo (1993) made similar observation of recording lowest temperature during the peak period of harmattan in Ado-Ekiti. Higher water temperatures during the dry season can be attributed probably to high atmospheric temperature, low relative humidity and reduction in the amount of suspended particles, that is, high transparency. Atobatele&Ugwumba (2008) reported that lower temperature recorded during December and January was attributed to the effect of harmattan wind while the highest temperature recorded during March was attributed to the peak of the dry season when insolation was at its highest. Similar observation was made in this study. Water temperature was lowest in December and highest in March. Similar reports have been made for Owena reservoir (Oke, 1998) Oyan and Asejire Lakes (Ayoade *et al.*, 2006) Ero Reservoir (Oso&Fagbuaro, 2008).

The result agreed with previous reports that the temperatures in tropics vary between 21°C and 32°C (Ugwumba and Ugwumba, 1993b; Ayoade& Ajani 1999; Kamra *et al.*, 2003; Ayoade *et al.*, 2006). Meske (1985) recommended temperature range of 20 – 30°C for optimum fish growth. This implies that the temperature range in Ado-Ekiti reservoir is suitable for fish growth.

Transparency of the water was lower during the period of heavy rainfall probably due to flooding of the reservoir, which may have been caused by higher amount of rainfall during this period due to high turbidity. It could also be due to decrease in sunlight intensity due to presence of heavy cloud in the atmosphere, which in turn reduced the quantity of light reaching the water (Anetekhai, 1986; Oso&Fagbuaro 2008) thereby decreasing light penetration. The higher transparency observed during the dry season could also be due to reduction in allochthonous substances that find their ways into the reservoir with flood (Ikomi *et al.*, 2003). Similar observations were made by Hassan (1974) in Awba Reservoir, Adebisi (1981) in Upper Ogun River, Egborge (1981) in Asejire Reservoir, Ikomi *et al.* (2003), in River Adofi, Idowu and Ugwumba (2005) in Eleyele Reservoir, Ayoade *et al.* (2006) in Asejire and Oyan lakes, Oso and Fagbuaro (2008) in Ero Reservoirs. Exception to the lower transparency experienced during the rainy season in the present study was in August 2003 when transparency was high probably due to the long "August break" for that year.

The pH of water is important because many biological activities can occur only within a narrow range. Thus, any variation beyond acceptable range could be fatal to a particular organism. The pH values were alkaline during the dry season and slightly acidic during the raining season. This has also been reported by some authors (Adebisi, 1981; Tyakumbur *et al.*, 2002; Ikomi *et al.*, 2003; Okogwu and Ugwumba, 2006). High pH during the dry season could be due to increase in photosynthetic activity during this period hence increasing primary productivity (Hammer, 1971). The pH values of the water in the reservoir fell within suitable range of 6.5 – 9.0 for fish production (Charkroff, 1976; Kamran *et al.*, 2003). Low pH is more probably a limiting factor in productivity than high pH (Lund, 1971).

Sources of dissolved oxygen in the aquatic environment include the atmospheric and photosynthesis and depend on its solubility while losses of oxygen include respiration, decay of aerobic bacteria and decomposition of dead decaying sediments (Gupta and Gupta, 2006). The high concentration of dissolved oxygen in the reservoir could be attributed to low organic enrichment. The low BOD values in the reservoir during the period of investigation, supports low organic enrichment of the reservoir (Manson, 1991; Idowu and Ugwumba, 2005; Idowu, 2007). The significant correlation between DO and transparency may have been due to high primary productivity which may have led to increase DO concentration (Manson, 1991). At alkaline pH values, photosynthetic activities would be high and should result in high oxygen content. Atobatele and Ugwumba (2008) reported that Hydrogen ion concentration (pH) in Aiba Reservoir showed a strong positive correlation with dissolved oxygen. Increasing levels of dissolved oxygen in aquatic systems are usually associated with eutrophic and productive water bodies (Egborge, 1994). The author attributed the decrease in dissolved oxygen observed in September during late wet season to phytoplankton bloom and decomposition of allochthonous organic materials taking place at this time of the year. The author further reported that Temperature showed a positive correlation with dissolved oxygen for the reservoir. Although there is usually inverse relationship between temperature and dissolved oxygen; exceptions do exist (Oben, 2000). Lewis (2000) opined that oxygen conservation is an important management principle for tropical lakes. Any observed depression in dissolved oxygen could be due to chemical and biological oxidation process in the water. Highest values of DO were recorded in this present work when temperature value was lowest. Lewis (2000) regarded factors that work against oxygen retention in tropical waters as the poorer ability of water to hold oxygen at higher temperature than at lower temperature and to the higher rates of microbial metabolism at higher temperature.

Water bodies of the tropics usually show a wide range of fluctuations in total alkalinity, the values depending on the location, season, plankton population and nature of bottom deposits. Highly productive waters have alkalinity values above 100ppm and for fresh water aquaculture, the values should be between 40 – 200ppm. Alkalinity values above 300ppm have been reported to adversely affect the spawning and hatching of freshwater fish (Gupta and Gupta, 2006). Idowu and Ugwumba (2005) reported high alkalinity values during the dry season. Similar observation was made in this study. The high values for most of the parameters recorded during the dry season and low values in the raining season correspond to the findings of some authors, in Southwestern Nigeria (Oke,1998 onOwena Reservoir; Idowu and Ugwumba,2008on Eleyele Reservoir; Ayoade *et al.*, 2006 on Oyan and Asejire lakes; Oso and Fagbuaro,2008 on Ero Reservoir and Atobatele and Ugumba in Aiba Reservoir respectively).

The insignificant correlation between abundance of *H. odoe* and physico-chemical parameters in the reservoir indicates abundance of *H. odoe* is independent of physico-chemical parameters. This is not surprising since all parameters examined in the reservoir were within recommended range for fish production and growth.

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